

1 **The androgen receptor is expressed abundantly in metastasis to the lungs and the CNS in humans**
2 **with metastatic breast cancer.**

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7 The study expands unbiased understanding of hormone receptor expression in human disease, like during
8 progression to metastatic disease at different organ sites.

9 Citations

10 1. Ni, M., Chen, Y., Lim, E., Wimberly, H., Bailey, S.T., Imai, Y., Rimm, D.L., Liu, X.S. and Brown, M.,
11 2011. Targeting androgen receptor in estrogen receptor-negative breast cancer. *Cancer cell*, 20(1),
12 pp.119-131.